

D6.2 Communication and Dissemination Report 1

October 2022 to September 2023

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Report overview

Project number	101073978
Project acronym	DIRECTED
Project name	Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing Interoperable Data, Models, Communication and Governance
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Topic	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-02
Type of action	Innovation Action
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Period covered	ALL
Reporting period number	1
Periodic report date and version	20/12/2023 - Final

Document history

Version	Date	Comment
V1	22.11.23	First full draft – Tracy Irvine
V2	19.12.23	Comments and Edits from all beneficiaries
V3	21.12.23	Final check and edits Max Steinhausen
V4	19.08.25	Reworked version for upload to Zenodo

Executive summary

This report reviews the communication and dissemination work that was conducted by the DIRECTED Project partners in the period between October 2022 to the End of September 2023. We have reported in direct relation to our original Communications and Dissemination Strategy submitted to Horizon Europe in March 2023.

The report includes updates on:

1. Our achievements towards our expected outcomes and impacts for the period October 2022 to September 2023
2. Our project communications activities in the period October 2022 to September 2023
3. Our project dissemination activities in the period October 2022 to September 2023
4. Individual partner communications and dissemination activities over the period October 2022 to September 2023
5. Planned activities for communications and dissemination for October 2023 to September 2024

In addition to this, we have also conducted work in producing a DIRECTED Project Storyboard that will assist partners in creating engaging content with strong and consistent messaging, as well as ensuring that communication and disseminations reach the actors who are most able to instigate the changes that are required to innovate the tools and governance changes developed by the DIRECTED Project and to assist us to reach our intended outcomes, outputs and impacts.

Our goals are to deliver a comprehensive communications and dissemination programme that engages, informs and influences our target audiences and enables us to move towards our outcomes and in the longer term see the impacts we wish to make. Specifically, our target audiences include:

- 1) First and second responders
- 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities
- 3) Physical and social scientific organisations - those who work in climate change, natural disaster sciences and damage and loss, governance and innovation
- 4) The general public - will be represented by municipalities

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1. Introduction

A broad Communication and Dissemination Strategy was submitted to Horizon Europe in March 2023 that set the first road map for the DIRECTED Project to succeed in reaching its stated goals and impacts supported by appropriate communication and dissemination actions. In this, our first annual communications and dissemination report, we will summarise communications and dissemination work for the period between October 2022 to September 2023. In addition, the report looks at how we intend to improve and enhance our communications and dissemination strategy as we progress in the Project. In this period, we have additionally developed a DIRECTED Storyboard – that will assist partners in creating engaging content with strong and consistent messaging, as well as ensuring that communication and dissemination reach the actors who can instigate the changes that are required to innovate the tools and governance changes developed by the DIRECTED Project and to assist us to reach our intended outcomes, outputs and impacts.

1.1 Background of the Directed Project

The recent droughts and unprecedented floods in central and southern Europe have illustrated our vulnerability to extreme weather events. Besides climate change as a driver of more frequent and intensifying weather extremes, demographic change and socio-economic development exacerbate severe impacts. International frameworks for Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation (e.g. SENDAI framework, EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change) acknowledge the critical need for integrating risk governance, communication, and operational mechanisms for coping with extreme climate events throughout the entire Disaster Risk Management cycle.

DIRECTED aspires to foster disaster-resilient European societies by expanding our capabilities to communicate, utilise and exchange state-of-the-art data, information and knowledge between different actors; boosting the integration, accessibility and interoperability of models; facilitating knowledge sharing; improving dialogue and cooperation encompassing all levels of actors based on enhanced community engagement and developing new governance and risk management strategies using a bottom-up, value-driven co-development approach. Key to supporting interoperability will be the establishment of the Data Fabric, an innovative, governed, cloud platform that enables secure, flexible, discovery and sharing of all structured and unstructured data. Thus, dissemination and communications are a core part of this project.

Central to DIRECTED are four Real World Labs that co-develop new governance, interoperability and knowledge production frameworks and demonstrate their benefits for enhanced disaster risk governance supported by innovative technical frameworks to access, transform and integrate data and models into customised workflows for creating actionable solutions. The Real World Labs ensure the project continuously and actively involves key stakeholders in the co-development process and address topical problems of multi-hazard risk management and Climate Change Adaptation to maximise impacts.

DIRECTED builds on a highly interactive transdisciplinary knowledge co-production process and an innovative digital architecture for process integration and analytics aimed at facilitating enhanced knowledge-based dialogues, communication, cooperation and “interoperability” on the three levels that are essential for integrating Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) related to extreme climate events in a multi-scale and multi-risk perspective: 1) Governance interoperability, 2) Information interoperability, and 3) Data and model interoperability (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The DIRECTED Project Concept.

For this aim, experts and expertise from the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), provided from within the consortium, play a crucial role. Governance interoperability seeks to integrate relevant actors, responders and stakeholders across institutions, sectors and scales through suitable governance and enabling mechanisms, suggestions for adjusted legal frameworks and tailored responsibilities and financing arrangements. Information interoperability pursues a verifiably and timely information exchange between all phases of the DRM cycle through improved dialogues and communication between DRR and CCA communities across multiple levels, such as resolving issues in understanding early warnings and turning relevant information into effective and coordinated actions.

In this regard, model-based information such as flood forecasts, Disaster Risk assessments, climate projections and cost-benefit analyses play a critical role in decision-support in different phases of the integrated DRM-CCA cycle. Data and model interoperability addresses the need for combining data and models (e.g. multi-risk), including proprietary resources, from/at different domains, providers, resolutions, vintages, sources, formats (and more) into highly customized DRR and CCA workflows given the frequent absence of standards, and the lack of a common understanding and infrastructure. This includes, but is not limited to, differences with respect to purpose, spatio-temporal scales, resolutions and conflicting model assumptions.

DIRECTED aims to pave the way for the generic use of existing state-of-the-art data and models combined by means of open standards for information and data exchange; and to demonstrate the feasibility thereof when available tools are made interoperable. Four RWLs

form the core of our DIRECTED approach and frame the settings for co-creating solutions and demonstrating integrated DRM and CCA, including our new and enhanced tools and processes.

Our four laboratories cover representative European geographies (Scandinavia, Central and Eastern Europe and the Mediterranean) and are characterized by a diversity of challenges from extreme climate events (including compound events), multi-risks, climate adaptation options, scales (from local to regional), and institutional and legal settings. This approach ensures that co-designing solutions to real-world challenges is central, and that stakeholder involvement occurs throughout the project.

1.2 Project partners

The DIRECTED Project has brought together a team of collaborators that cover different areas of work including physical and social science research organisations and sit in a range of different sectors including (R) Research, (L) local or regional authorities, (P) practitioners, (C) commercial / private sector (See Table 1). As a group, from a dissemination and communication perspective, we have large existing networks in the research & academic, commercial, local authorities and emergency services who we intend to engage, disseminate and where appropriate involve in the Project. We also intend to grow these networks through different communication platforms and techniques.

Table 1: List of participant: (R) Research, (L) local or regional authorities, (P) practitioners, (C) commercial / private sector.

N°	ROLE	SECTOR	SHORT NAME	LEGAL NAME	COUNTRY
1	COO	R	TUBS	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG	DE
2	BEN	R	PIK	POTSDAM-INSTITUT FUR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG EV	DE
3	BEN	R	DTU	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DK
4	BEN	C	GECO	GECOSISTEMA SRL	IT
5	BEN	R	RIFS	RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR SUSTAINABILITY	DE
6	BEN	R	UCC	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	IE
7	BEN	L	REGIONH	REGION HOVEDSTADEN	DK
8	BEN	P	ARSTPC-ER	AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA SICUREZZATERRITORIALE E LA PROTEZIONE CIVILE	IT
9	BEN	C	G&C	GENILLARD & CO GMBH	DE
10	BEN	R	IIASA	INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE	AT
11	BEN	L	EV	ERFTVERBAND	DE
12	BEN	P	ZSRT	ZALA KULONLEGES MENTOK ES ONKENTES TUZOLTO EGYSULET	HU
13	BEN	P	ARPAE	AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA PREVENZIONE, L'AMBIENTE E L'ENERGIA DELL'EMILIA-ROMAGNA	IT
14	BEN	R	GFZ	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM POTSDAM DEUTSCHESGEOFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GFZ	DE
15	BEN	C	52N	52 NORTH SPATIAL INFORMATION RESEARCH GMBH	DE
16	AP	R	ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH
17	AP	C	OASIS	OASIS HUB LIMITED	UK
18	AP	R	SEI	SEI OXFORD OFFICE LIMITED	UK

1.3 Expected outcomes & impacts

The Directed Project has set itself some ambitious objectives to achieve within the four years of the Project and beyond. In this part of the report we will summarise early/ Year 1 outcomes for the Project that will be highlighted in the green boxes.

1.3.1 Outcomes and indicators of scale and significance

Outcome 1 Improved dialogue and cooperation among scientific and technical communities, stakeholders, policymakers, and local communities in the field of extreme climate events and associated events (e.g. forest fires, droughts, floods, heatwaves and storms) and Disaster Risk Reduction.

Output 1: Using the Risk-Tandem Assessment Technique we will increase the interactions, co-exploration, coproduction with transdisciplinary stakeholders in the DRR/ CCA sectors (including first & second responders, planners, scientists, media, utilities, social services & NGO's) - through the creation of four Real World Labs – assisting the development of long-term working relationships; understanding roles, responsibilities, dependencies, barriers to improvements and efficiencies needed.

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

Training has been conducted on the use of the Risk-Tandem approach to the Real World Lab leaders during;

1. Online exchanges with RWLs ahead of their stakeholder workshops (Feb - May 2023) including a recorded video explainer and briefing notes and suggested workshop materials/tools)
2. A scientific exchange about the hydrological/hydrodynamic modelling of the Sava and Drava rivers in Croatia has been established between PIK and Prof. Kristina Potočki of the University of Zagreb. It is planned to exchange modelling data, results, and expert knowledge over the next years.
3. A one-day hands-on Risk-Tandem training workshop at the Directed General Assembly (21/10/23) demonstrating knowledge co-production approaches including role-play games and creative co-exploration of stakeholders' needs and DRR/CCA solutions. These training activities enabled further application in the wider running of the Labs.

Indicator 1: Real World Lab case studies and summary reports used by DRR/CCA stakeholders for planning purposes

Scale of contribution – The Risk-Tandem Assessment Technique will enable the building of consensus approaches towards Disaster Risk Management, Reduction and Climate Adaptation for the four regions of the Real World Labs: the Danube River Basin, covering the multiple municipalities – in city and countryside contexts, Copenhagen and Capital Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy, and the Rhine-Erft Region, Germany

Outcome 2 Enhanced community engagement for prevention, preparedness, response, recovery and learning to extreme climate events by strengthening knowledge and involvement of volunteers linked to recognised organisations into the planning, design and implementation of prevention, including building with nature, preparedness and emergency response activities.

Output 2: A Co-production methodology for disaster resilience will be developed and used by at least two municipalities increasing the connections and engagement of volunteers in the planning, design and implementation of prevention, including building with nature, preparedness and emergency response activities.

Indicator 2: Co-produced planning reports scale of contribution – Disaster Resilience Planning Reports will be developed and included in local planning in Copenhagen and Capital Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy and the Rhine-Erft Region, Germany

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

No action this year.

This outcome will begin to be actioned in June 2024, linked to a full-scale simulation of an extreme event in Emilia-Romagna, with first responders, local authorities and volunteers.

Outcome 3 Strengthening of Disaster Risk Reduction and resilience building through innovative use of media means, namely by examining the potential of new communication tools and apps for better preparedness and response.

Output 3a: A Data Fabric/ mesh/ ecosystem – and linked tools, developed into workflows, that enable the rapid delivery of relevant information, data, maps etc. to relevant stakeholders e.g. maps of potential areas at risk using forecast information for risk assessment to early responders or communications for mass media delivered with warning visualisations or integration of data sources for Climate Change Adaptation etc.

Indicator 3a: workflows will be utilised by Real World Lab participant stakeholders to improve current processes

Output 3b: Visualisations – Simple communications in the form of visualisations of threat level, action required and how to get communications on hazard events will be developed for the general public consumption – enabling faster actions of citizens to prepare for climate events – for 3 municipalities. Indicator 3b: Visualisations disseminated to general public online, social media &/or via printed mailings

Scale of contribution – The Data Fabric/ mesh/ ecosystem will provide a prototype system and tools enabling replicable workflows of work including multiple stakeholder organisations, all types of quantitative and qualitative: including data, maps, visualisations and text formats for communications to diverse stakeholders. The system is intended to radically reform and improve the management and communications for disaster management, risk assessment and adaptation planning enabling actionable decisions using complex and multiple data sources. We intend for this tools to be replicated across Europe and beyond.

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

Initial Real World Lab meetings have been held including the RWL leadership and 52N, the Data Fabric designers. This has identified some of the existing local tools used by the RWL in different regions to begin to understand how they could be built into the Data Fabric.

The co-production process with the Real World Lab stakeholders will begin in Oct 2023/ Sept 2024.

Outcome 4 Overview of existing knowledge, tools and development of new tools (innovative data collection, satellite data, data harmonisation, artificial-intelligence tools, algorithms, sensors and decision-aid approaches) for early warning, response and resilience / adaptation to be demonstrated in the framework of real-case scenarios designed for training addressed to first and second responders, (national, regional, local) authorities and populations. The overview should document how legal and ethical rules of operation as well as fundamental rights such as privacy and protection of personal data are taken into account.

Output 4: Forecasting and risk assessment, and adaptation tools made interoperable to increase functionality and multi-risk outputs necessary for seamless early warning, risk assessment and risk reduction strategy decision-making. The tool collaboration will have the capability to be used for training and implementation of Disaster Risk Management.

Indicator 4: Use of interoperable systems by DRR and CCA authorities to assist training, planning and decision making

Scale of contribution – From within the Project a range of existing tools in flood risk assessment, adaptation planning, forecasting, citizen App will be enabled to become interoperable – thus improving multi-hazard risk assessment capabilities and functions – on top of this the work on interoperability is set to develop a standard so that multiple tools and

data from beyond the project can also become interoperable in the future and in doing so improve access to and functionality of single use tools into a multi-hazard ecosystem for decision support for multiple stakeholders across sectors and European regions and beyond.

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

This part of the Project will begin in October 2023/ September 2024. Some stocktaking of data sources and web platforms has already been pursued in preparation of Deliverable 2.1

Outcome 5 Based on the demonstrations, development of new governance strategies and robust decision-support methodologies for integrated risk reduction and improved adaptation to climate extreme events.

Output 5: Data Fabric/ mesh that enables the sharing, management and communication to relevant stakeholders in useable formats of complex information, data, maps and risk assessment – managed through one multi-partner system. Indicator 5: – Governance workflows agreed by stakeholders and implemented into management system/ Data Fabric

Scale of contribution – Governance workflows on a range of case studies will be implemented in the Danube River Basin, covering the multiple municipalities – in city and countryside contexts, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy, Copenhagen and Capital Region, and the Rhine-Erft Region, Germany

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

This part of the Project will begin in October 2023/ September 2024.

Outcome 6 Improved understanding of enablers and barriers to multi-risk governance frameworks and multi-risk thinking, by involving interdisciplinary teams in different fields, particularly the social and behavioural sciences.

Output 6: Policy brief on risk governance in the context of DRR and CCA highlighting barriers and potential solutions to improve multi-risk governance.

Indicator 6: Uptake of recommendations from policy brief by at least one DRR/CCA agency

Scale of contribution – The EC and national policy-makers in Germany, Hungary and Italy will have access to findings and results of the DIRECTED Project. We envisage this will assist future governance of disasters and climate adaptation planning.

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

This part of the Project will begin in later in the project.

Outcome 7 Cost-benefit or cost-effectiveness analyses of investment and regulatory strategies to protect people and nature in vulnerable areas.

Output 7: Cost-benefit analysis of Climate Change Adaptation/ Disaster Risk Reduction measures made for at least 2 municipalities during the project.

Indicator 7: Cost-benefit analysis of Climate Change Adaptation / Disaster Risk Reduction measures for at least 2 municipality used in future planning document or applications for adaptation funding for Climate Change Adaptation / Disaster Risk Reduction

Scale of contribution – Two municipalities will have conducted cost/ benefit analysis of potential Climate Change Adaptation actions enabling a strong needs analysis of multiple Climate Change Adaptation solutions that increases the potential for investment

Beyond to Project outcomes above the project is intended to lead to a range of intended impacts some of which will begin during the Project and others that should continue beyond the life of the Project.

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

This part of the Project will begin in 2024/ 2025 period.

1.3.2 Intended Impacts

Scientific: The DIRECTED Project will assist the scientific community in stocktaking of standards for the interoperability of data and models, identifying gaps and requirements to exchange information between different phases of DRM/ CCA cycle and across hazards and integrating quantitative and qualitative indicators. This will assist the scientific community with providing an interoperability framework that enables future tool development that can become part of a wider network for decision making data, tools and systems increasing the potential to provide actionable intelligence based on data and information from multiple sources by the DRR and CCA community.

Through the production of workflow processes within the Project – the provision at what stages, to whom and in what format scientific information is included and communicated will be an impact of the Project providing collaboration between sectors that do not traditionally have access to science and scientists directly, likely to become a policy recommendation moving forward, thus increasing access to actionable science by all levels of government and society.

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

Work has begun on a compendium on data standards for interoperability in DRR and CCA is due for completion in September 2024.

Economic: the DIRECTED Project outputs will contribute a range of economic impacts in the future:

- The breakdown of silos e.g. between cross-boundary municipalities, between multiple stakeholder groups in the DRR/CCA process will increase the economic efficiency of work and linked funding by creating more seamless workflows, preventing duplication of spend on the same actions with the potential to more carefully budget and target spend across actors and locations.
- Work that has enabled the interoperability of multiple forms of data and tools into producing multi-risk, risk assessment and Climate Change Adaptation solutions plus linked cost-benefit analysis will increase the potential to implement adaptation actions, targeted at locations most at risk, thus reducing the overall spend required to enable increased resilience by society.
- Losses from climate disasters are reduced through enhanced Disaster Risk Reduction based on preventive actions, better societal preparedness and resilience and improved Disaster Risk Management in a systemic way – with the potential to reduce losses significantly over time in the regions of billions of Euros

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

Nothing to report at this early stage of the project.

Societal: The DIRECTED Project outputs will also contribute to societal impacts in the future:

- Losses from climate disasters are reduced through enhanced Disaster Risk Reduction based on preventive actions, better societal preparedness and resilience and improved Disaster Risk Management in a systemic way.
- Enabling scientific outputs to more rapidly be utilised by DRR/CCA actors and also directly communicated to the general public – helping to inform potential for damage and then actions required across society including at household & business levels to reduce the impact of climate-related catastrophes.
- Supporting first, second and third responders with forecast and risk assessment information they need to utilise emergency services more effectively – understanding the likelihood of the most impacted zones after a disaster and conditions associated with that emergency e.g. flood levels, types of properties and multiple other data sources as brought together by interoperable tools and the Data Fabric/ mesh
- Supporting first, second and third responders with training materials enabling more efficient responses to climate emergencies

Update for October 2022/ September 2023

In May 2023 major floods occurred in the Emilia-Romagna Region, one of the Real World Labs, that resulted in loss of life, the displacement of thousands of people and 8.8 billion in damages.

Between 16-18 May 2023, 350 million cubic metres of water, equivalent to six months' worth of rain, fell within 36 hours across Emilia-Romagna, one of Italy's most important agricultural regions. The heavy rain led to the overflow of 23 rivers across the region, affecting 100 municipalities and triggering more than 400 landslides, which in turn damaged and closed off hundreds of roads. The floods were preceded by a drought that dried out the land, reducing its capacity to absorb water.

The SaferPlaces Platform, was utilised by the Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region to generate flood water and depth maps to take crucial decisions after the disaster and support the assessment of the damages of the affected areas. The platform utilised satellite, climate data and AI-based models combined into a cloud computing environment to provide insights into areas prone to floods across the globe.

Information on the flooded areas and the affected buildings conducted by local municipalities and data provided by the Emilia-Romagna Civil Protection were also integrated to fill the gaps and increase the accuracy of urban flooded areas when not captured by satellites. Maps portraying the extent of the flooded areas in the most affected municipalities, Faenza, Cesena, Forlì and Conselice, were generated with information on the depth and volume of the water.

These maps provided crucial information for a preliminary Flood Damage Assessment to support the local and central authorities to estimate the damages as soon as possible. Specifically, the satellite-based water depth maps were used as input to assess the economic losses of affected buildings.

Claudia Vezzani, Technical Manager of the Hydraulic Risk Area of the Civil Protection Agency of Emilia-Romagna Region, highlighted: "SaferPlaces technology and Earth observation data allow us to usefully support the disaster analyses and the computation of economic losses."

1.4 Target Groups for Communication and Dissemination

DRR and CCA communities involve multiple stakeholder groups, all requiring information for different purposes and at different levels of communication. Likewise, the work undertaken involves different time dimensional needs e.g. disaster information during a disaster and the need for risk reduction and climate adaptation planning. We seek to reduce complexity and increase efficiency to access the relevant information and data needs through understanding and creating appropriate workflows where we will seek to link appropriate climate science outputs and information to make operational decisions at the appropriate time, e.g. risk reduction and adaptation planning or for training and preparation or operational response. We have carefully selected representational organisations of our target groups to be directly involved as co-production, co-design partners in the Project.

Our target groups include:

- 1) first and second responders
- 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross-regional municipalities
- 3) Physical and social scientific organisations - those who work in climate change, natural disaster sciences and damage and loss, governance and innovation
- 4) The general public - will mainly be represented by municipalities

The Real World Labs will invite other local stakeholders including utility companies, NGOs, health and social care organisations to become part of the consultations. We perceive that the four RWL's: in the Danube catchment basin, Germany, Italy and Scandinavia will be representative of stakeholders from across Europe to ensure the potential for scalability of governance structures, the use of interoperable tools and management via Data Fabric/ mech digital architectures.

Beyond the work of the Project directly, we intend to engage stakeholders who will benefit from knowledge of the techniques used in the Project, as well as the tools used within the system and the Data Fabric itself from the four communities named above, and extended beyond the regions involved in the Project.

Section 2: Report on Communications October 2022 to September 2023

In this section we will report on progress towards our original communications and dissemination goals for October 2022 to September 2023.

As per our original proposal we had drafted a broad communications timeline as per Table 2. We will report on this table, as well as the targets we have set for each dissemination and communications activity, as below.

Table 2: Directed communications timeline.

Phase 1 Oct 2022 to March 2023	Phase 2 March 2023 to March 2024	Phase 3 March 2024 to March 2025	Phase 4 March 2025 to March 2026	Phase 5 March 2026 to October 2026
<p>Communications strategy developed</p> <p>Project launch communications</p> <p>Start of Project Blog – quarterly blog posts to continue to end of the Project</p> <p>Bi-weekly social media posts began and continued to the end of the Project e.g. stories, plans etc.</p> <p>Website development</p> <p>Brand development</p>	<p>Communications on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project events • Workshops • Processes and techniques and the physical and social scientists/ themselves • Building a picture of the people involved in Directed stakeholder involvement and outcomes during this phase <p>Continued social media dissemination</p> <p>Beginning of conference dissemination</p>	<p>Communications on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early scientific & governance and process • Findings from market research and stakeholder needs assessment • Real World Lab reports <p>Continued conference dissemination</p> <p>Continued social media dissemination</p> <p>Case study creation</p>	<p>Research publications and related news and articles</p> <p>Training material and programme on use of tools and systems</p> <p>Webinar series with physical and social scientists</p> <p>Continued social media dissemination</p> <p>Media pack creation & dissemination (press releases for international media)</p>	<p>Policy-maker meetings, policy briefs.</p> <p>Conference dissemination of results</p> <p>Continued social media dissemination</p>

Using the Communications and Dissemination Strategy we have reported on the actions and outputs so far in terms of communications and dissemination function within the DIRECTED

Project. A report on communications work from individual organizations is also included later in the report.

2.2 Communications

2.2.1 Project launch

A Project Launch has been conducted in conjunction with our first meeting in November, 2022. A social media campaign was conducted by all of the partners making the announcement on multiple social media channels and websites. Here we have reported on the Communications Lead activity and results and later report on individual grant beneficiaries' communications.

Table 3: Communication of project launch.

Article	Link	Impressions	Reactions	Comments	Reposts	Article views	Job Titles	Locations
New Horizon Europe Project set to improve climate Disaster Risk Management across civil authorities and first responders in Europe	DIRECTED Launch LinkedIn – Oasis Hub	2293	34	6	2	285	University Professor / Lecturer 21% Founder 17.8% Consultant 6.5% Laboratory Scientist 4.7% Project Manager 3.6%	London Area, United Kingdom 22.5% Greater Reno Area 15.9% Copenhagen Metropolitan Area 9.1% Cologne Bonn Region 4% Greater Aarhus Area 4%

Activity completed.

2.2.2 Project branding & website

Project branding has been developed to enable easy recognition of the DIRECTED Project and to ensure that the Project is recognised as one rather than a series of smaller projects.

The DIRECTED Logo and branding will be used on all DIRECTED communications.

Figure 2: Directed Logo.

We have designed branded communication templates for reports, policy briefs, conference posters and pull-outs using DIRECTED branding which all the participants in the project will use.

Importantly we have designed a DIRECTED Project website. The website includes a wide range of communication channels including a regular blog, news, publications, reports, videos, podcasts, Press information and webinars. To ease and assist communications, partners will be able to copy links or download materials and post to organisational media outlets.

Figure 3: Directed Website.

The Project URL can be found here: <https://directedproject.eu/>

The site disseminates full information and progress of the Project, as well as more contextual information on climate Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation.

In addition, we have made it a central communications and dissemination hub in that all of our social media will be connected to the website, project reports, videos and podcasts, webinars, publications and presentations can be stored and viewed on the site.

Table 4: Target v Actual for communication action Oct 2022 to Oct 2023.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Actual October 2023	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
All	30,000 Users over 4 years	Total users Yr 1 Website users 4222 since 14. February 2023 website launch – more details to come 2023 as full google analytics will be implemented in Oct 2023 e.g. audiences, reach, countries etc.	Users from google analytics	Outcomes 1,2,3,4,5,6,7 Broad communication of reports, videos, podcasts, webinars, papers, news, presentations

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024:

- Implementation of Google Analytics to obtain greater audience details on our online audiences.
- Improvement to website to include Product Solutions, links to sister EU Projects, Film on Homepage, Area for press information

- Publication of deliverable reports, presentations and multi-media
- Communications via news and quarterly blogs

2.2.3 Real World Labs/ Case study creation

Case studies are being developed as a part of the Real World Labs. The idea of the case studies is to publish information and experiences of grassroots professionals when working on climate Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation and include process successes and failures and communications issues that have occurred during and after disasters and in the facilitation of cross border Climate Change Adaptation planning and action. This year we have chosen to focus the Case Studies on a comparison between the Rhine-Erft Flood events 2021 and of the Emilia-Romagna, major floods of 2023. These two high-profile flood events are likely to attract interest from first responders and disaster practitioners and policymakers in understanding organisation response, results and potential improvement for the future.

We hope this will enable other professionals in DRR/CCA to recognise the friction in their own processes and potential ways to overcome and improve these. This work will also inform the development of the Data Fabric.

In 2022 – Oct 2023 we began collecting the data and information required to develop the case studies and agreed on a draft index. The deliverable date for the case studies is Sept 2024 and therefore the case study development is ongoing.

2.2.4 Visualisations

Visualisations for the general public will be designed for effective communications of stages of risk decision for public information to enable a simple understanding on the processes of risk e.g. prepare, evacuate, where to find official communication, level of flood that sparks decision stages – these will be designed in local languages and for the local context for the RWL’s

This deliverable will begin in year 3/ 4 of project.

Table 5: Visualization for RWLs.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
General Public	Reach 2000 households per each RWL case study area	Downloads	Outcome 3 General public informed of disaster decision-making process and where to get information

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024:

This deliverable has not yet begun.

2.2.5 Social media

New DIRECTED Project social media have been created and developed including;

- LinkedIn discussion group – we will use this as a key dissemination forum inviting DRR & CCA specialists to the forum to engage and collaborate with us. We will also use LinkedIn to poll members on key questions that will benefit our work – thus gaining input from a wider range of stakeholders. We see linked in as the medium to engage a large network of professionals in the fields of DRR and CCA

Find us on LinkedIn - <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/14155514/>

- YouTube for video
Find us on YouTube - @directedproject
- Twitter & Mastodon – we will build communities in both Twitter and Mastodon. We are using both as it is unclear whether Twitter will keep its top status and whether it will be able to continue long-term. Mastodon also targets specialist user groups. These channels will primarily be aimed at communicating to the general public.

Find us on Twitter and Mastodon

Twitter - @DirectedProj

Mastodon - <https://vmst.io/@DirectedProject>

- Instagram – has been chosen as it is used by the younger people. We will be posting small videocasts and visualisations informing people about our project. Again, we will use this to inform new audiences in particular younger people.

Find us on Instagram - <https://www.instagram.com/directedproject/>

These channels are being developed by following other stakeholder organisations and relevant influencers as well as linking to our partners social medias. Relevant hashtags will be identified and used to attract other relevant followers.

We will also communicate information throughout our project members existing social media channels some beneficiaries having large existing members/ followers and link to these channels with social media posts.

New audiences will be targeted through linking to particular influencers in relevant sectors – new target sectors will include risk managers in municipalities, local authorities and services, policy-makers, DRR professionals and local planning departments and specific targets as they become clear after the ideation/ market research/ user needs engagement in the Project.

Table 6: Social media communication.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Actual at October 2023	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impacts
All	Reach users: LinkedIn – 200 external DRR & CCA professionals YouTube – create at least five short videos and gain 100 subscribers on YouTube Twitter and Mastodon develop followers on both platforms of 500 Instagram gain 500 followers	New LinkedIn 58 members since Dec 2022 New YouTube Channel created – one 14 min film posted – 31.08.23 – 109 views, 2 subscribers New Twitter/ X channel created – Jan 2023 – 91 followers New Mastodon channel created -Jan 2023– 5 followers New Instagram created – Jan 2023 – 42 followers	Analytic indicators provided on each platform	Outcomes 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

We established channels in January, 2023 and are now posting on a regular basis to these social media. LinkedIn appears to be the most positively received channel, which would be expected, as it consists of professionals who are interested in the work DIRECTED is undertaking. On X/ formerly twitter we have been gradually growing and tend to be followed by other Projects of a similar nature – therefore this is ideal to act as a dissemination channel, in terms of enabling learning from what we are achieving.

However, since the Elon Musk takeover X appears to be unstable in terms of the potential of what will happen in the future – e.g. talk of making it into a banking and dating app have been floated – thus we will need to keep a close eye on its continual development. It may be wise to set up channels on other/ new social media platforms to establish which channels might take over X’s former dominance. Mastodon has not really worked for us at this point and it may be better to focus on other channels. We have posted our first film on YouTube gaining 109 views so far, but this should continue to rise, as the video will be placed on the website homepage.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024:

- Based on DIRECTED Storyboard (see page 40) – plan social media content/ stories for year 2023/ 2024 – Improving outputs and stories.
- Spend time continuing to follow and engage with relevant social media influencers.

- Ensure all media teams of beneficiary’s partners in the Project are provided with relevant communications links for reposting/ responding to posts to boost viewing of DIRECTED Communications.

2.2.6 Video, Podcasts & Webinars

Webinar series will be designed for specific sectors in phase 4 of the project communications with the physical and social scientists, and local governance actors engaged in the project, presenting and talking to specifically targeted sectors and then further engagement by Oasis Hub of attendees in encouraging the use of outputs by those stakeholders engaged in the webinars. In addition, the recordings of the webinars will be shared on YouTube and the DIRECTED website.

Table 7: Video, Podcasts and webinars.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Actual Yr 1	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impacts
Webinars 1) First and second responders 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities 3) Physical and social scientific organisations	100 attendees x 4 webinars aimed at specialist groups	Webinars not due for implementation	Attendees’ engagement as collected in Zoom analytics Resulting engagements/ links/ collaboration after webinars	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7
Videos & podcasts All	At least 6 x videos and podcasts placed on website and YouTube & Instagram – and shared on other platforms Reaching 600+ viewers	1x14 min Introductory video DIRECTED INTRO VIDEO Published 31 st August, 2023 - 113 viewers	Analytics from google analytics, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, Mastodon on message containing videos or podcast	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Short videos and podcasts will record a range of aspects of the Project including a short introductory video and then longer more detailed videos as the Project progresses.

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

We have created an initial project video entitled ‘Scientists, Municipalities and Emergency Responders are improving the Management of Climate Extremes. This video is an intimate portrayal of some of the scientists and public servants working in the DIRECTED Partnership and what, why and how the DIRECTED Project will improve Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation. The video was posted on 31st August, 2023 and has currently received 113 public views.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024:

- Short 3 min – intro video for DIRECTED – for distribution when requested
- Develop DIRECTED content related podcast/ webinar plan – aim for three in 2023/24
- Podcasts/ webinars to include Real World Lab Reports and Project tools e.g. Risk-Tandem, serious games and the physical risk tools

2.2.7 Quarterly Blog

Blogs will be used as a medium to fully engage audiences in a more detailed fashion. These will include information about the Projects, about results and discussions of Real World Labs, what a Data Fabric is, information on the scientific tools within the Project and much more.

Blogs will be posted at a minimum on a quarterly basis, at the beginning of the Project but will increase as activity and outputs increase in the Project.

Table 8: Blogs published on the website and social media.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Actual Year 1	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist users – including DRR & CCA professionals	20,000 articles views on specialist channels	<p>2 x Blogs posted since website launch in Feb 2023</p> <p>https://directedproject.eu/blog/moving-out-of-the-silos/</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>1027 impressions/ 22 likes, 2 reposts, 1 comment on T Irvine/ OasisHub</p> <p>DIRECTProjectGroup (DPG) – 263 impressions, 1 like</p> <p>https://directedproject.eu/blog/real-world-lab-capital-region-of-denmark/</p> <p>LinkedIn</p> <p>-990 impressions, 88 article views, 13 Likes, 2 Reposts - on T Irvine/ OasisHub</p> <p>276 views of Blog section of website</p> <p>Google analytics currently being implemented.</p>	Article views	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6, 7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

Two blogs have been delivered since we created the original Communications and Dissemination Strategy, this is one less than intended.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

The Blog during 2023/2024 will be guided by the DIRECTED Storyboard.

Our next scheduled blogs include, but are not limited to:

1. Blog on The Connectivity Hub
2. Blog on Rhine Erft
3. Blog on Serious Gaming
4. Blog on Emilia-Romagna Real World Lab.
5. Blog on Danube Real World Lab

2.2.8 Mass Media and Media Pack Creation

Press releases will be released on activities that may be of interest to broad audiences to local medias on the activities of the Real World Labs. Later on in the Project as results become available and more outcomes are achieved editorials will be pitched to specialist medias e.g. insurance, climate change and DRR specialist publications.

Media Packs – will be designed for digital distribution to specialist on-line media portals e.g. insurance magazines, EU Adapt and other EU comms platforms, and medias targeted at Cities and public authorities and the international media. These packs will contain case studies and press releases related to specific outputs of the DIRECTED Project. A major media campaign will occur in the 4th phase of the communications plan when results are ready to be published. If we believe there are stories that will potentially be high profile media, we will inform the EU Project Officer in the planning stage or if something is picked up unexpectedly, as soon as possible.

Table 9: Mass media and media pack.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Actual Year 1	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Mass media – General Public	25 Media packs downloaded	Articles published	3 out of 4 Real World Labs prepared in English – not yet posted in website as waiting for 4 th leaflet preparation	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

Press information has been prepared for the Rhine-Erft, Emilia-Romagna and the Danube Region Real World Labs. When the fourth Real World Lab (Denmark) information is prepared it will be placed in the Press info part of the website. These leaflets will be updated when necessary and will also be translated into local languages.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

Completion of Danish Leaflet in English.

All leaflets to be translated into local languages.

Prepare press releases for relevant RWL meetings – at least two to be completed in 2023/24.

2.3 Dissemination

2.3.1 Tool Demonstrations

As a part of the programme there will be a need to demonstrate a range of newly developed climate change risk assessment, Climate Change Adaptation and disaster management tools within the Real World Labs and the organisations represented in them. This will enable the DRR and CCA practitioners to more clearly understand some of the new tools developed in the previous H2020 programmes and via other programmes and companies to seek advice from CCA and DRR practitioners how they would like the tools to be made interoperable and what additional parameters should be added to make them more useful.

Table 10: Tool demonstrations.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Actual Year 1	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist audiences	At least 16 presentations of tools & services made to real world practitioners	Number of presentations and members in the audience		Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

Ideas regarding the future monitoring and modelling of drought effects in the Danube region were demonstrated by PIK on 28 April 2023 at the EGU General Assembly in Vienna, Austria, using the example from a previous research project, CROSSDRO, assessing the 2018–2020 drought in the Elbe River basin.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

The refurbished version of PIK's Danube Model has been initially presented outside the Directed Consortium by Christopher Genillard (G&C) on 11 October 2023 in Budapest, Hungary, at the biannual Danube Forecasting Forum (DAFF) organized in collaboration with the International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River (ICPDR) and the EU Joint Research Centre (EU JRC). Other international conferences like the annual EGU General Assembly in Vienna, Austria, are intended to further showcase PIK's modelling activities in Directed.

2.3.2 Stakeholder engagement in codesign and co-production

DIRECTED will put co-creation and co-production at its heart, by applying the Tandem approach of transdisciplinary knowledge co-production with a risk governance lens, resulting in Risk-Tandem. The Tandem philosophy represents a major shift away from a focus on 'products' to a transdisciplinary knowledge co-production 'process' in which co-design and collaborative learning is the defining characteristic, and both stakeholders and modellers alike build their capacity to understand the decision context and the potential of data and tools. The use of Tandem guides stakeholders from across the science-society interface, with diverse knowledge, expertise and experience to collaborate, co-design activities and co-produce knowledge and data for models and tools to provide context-specific input to Climate Change Adaptation plans and policies. With a risk governance lens, Risk-Tandem will act as a lever to bring knowledge on co-design and co-development to the core of model development processes to support more effective decision-making and serve as a mechanism for facilitating participation, engagement, and communication. Transdisciplinary co-production, knowledge exchange and learning processes will be designed to enhance and reconcile key aspects of "interoperability" that currently serves as a barrier for effective DRR.

Figure 4 shows how the current Tandem framework supports different Work Packages in Directed. The Risk-Tandem Framework will be a version tailored for application in the RWLs and further refined and improved over the lifetime of the project.

Figure 4: Directed Work Packages linked to the Tandem Framework.

Table 11: Stakeholder engagement.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Actual Year 1	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist audiences	Detailed stakeholder engagement for co-design and co-production in conjunction with four Real World Labs	Number of specialists involved in workshops	12 RWL hosts engaged in co-production training	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

Work toward stakeholder engagement through co-production and co-design began in January 2023, starting with the first draft of Risk-Tandem (including the approach to integrating co-production within existing risk governance tools and frameworks). This formed the foundation for engagement with the RWLs, including a theoretical premise on advancing transdisciplinary complex risk management approaches, and associated activities such as stakeholder mapping and analysis. The process thus far has followed the Tandem Framework’s structure guiding co-production, and RWLs have now completed many of the early steps regarding setting priorities for their working context, stakeholder identification and engagement, as well as some activities for the co-exploration of disaster and climate risks in situ. First learning module regarding complex systems and systemic risk management was delivered in June 2023, and co-production methods for co-exploration and issue prioritization demonstrated in

this workshop were tested by RWL hosts in Emilia-Romagna, reportedly with great results. Co-production approaches were also integrated into the agenda of the 2023 consortium meeting in Cologne, with a particular emphasis on serious games and unstructured methods dedicated to unpacking perspectives of partners regarding the project's future directions (and challenges they may face during the process).

In September 2023, WP 4 finalized the capacity development strategy for DIRECTED, outlining how co-production – as imagined within Risk-Tandem – will be operationalized through training of trainers. In short, WP 3 and WP 4 will join their efforts to upskill RWL hosts to implement and design co-production activities in workshops to support transdisciplinary engagement in the context of risk governance, seeking to integrate DRR and CCA, and balancing issues relating to the interoperability of modelling systems (thus also contributing to the Data Fabric). The latter aspect will emphasize user needs vis-à-vis existing modelling capabilities, in efforts to improve the contextual accuracy and use of products developed by DIRECTED partners.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

For Q4 of 2023 and Q1 of 2024, the focus will be on finalizing the Risk-Tandem Framework with the help of already gathered information and data, and aligning it with the priorities of RWLs, partners and other deliverables. The capacity needs assessment will be launched to further assess and contextualize the approach to training of trainers, with an emphasis on current RWL needs. This will be accompanied by complimentary efforts (such as Q-survey assessments) dedicated to further understanding the local risk governance context for increased impact and effectiveness. Informed by these capacity development modules for the RWL hosts will be designed and launched, potentially focusing on stakeholder engagement methods (outreach to representatives of vulnerable groups, for instance), facilitation skills and ethics pertaining to work under DIRECTED (latter a gap that has been identified in the context of running workshops and co-production activities). It is intended that by M36, a comprehensive series on operationalizing co-production in the context of risk reduction is finalized and made available through DIRECTED's knowledge transfer activities as outlined in Deliverable 6.3. regarding Gaps and Opportunities (as discussed in chapter 2.3.4).

2.3.3 Policy Briefs & Policy-maker Meetings

Policy briefs will be created using the results of the DIRECTED Project to make recommendations towards EU and local Disaster Risk, economic and climate adaptation policies. A briefing of the results of the Project will be conducted in phase 5 of the Project to relevant EU Departments and Executive Agencies (DG's) – we will also seek an understanding whether relevant DGs would seek to be kept up-to-date in the progress of the project e.g. how & when. Likewise, policy briefs can also be distributed amongst local level policy stakeholders to guide policy as appropriate.

Table 12: Policy briefs and meetings.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Policy-makers and senior civil servants	At end of project deliver policy implications for governance and transfer of climate change science to the DRR/CCA communities across Europe	Number of policy-makers and senior civil servants attending meeting Downloads of policy briefs	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

Not yet started.

2.3.4 DIRECTED e-Learning Portal

Development of programmes that combine information and learning related elements of governance frameworks that can be supported by innovative technical frameworks to access, transform and integrate data and models into customised workflows for creating actionable solutions.

Programmes will target vocational long-life training to support the Real World Labs, student support materials and provide support and help build risk and adaptation solutions, especially those identified by Real World Labs.

In order to perpetuate learning programmes, a co-designed and co-developed “Training of Trainers” programme will be developed through a dedicated Workshop with trainers, and curriculum developed in response to needs, so that capability beyond the DIRECTED project is ensured. Workshops delivered both in-person and online will be highly participatory and practical, focusing on techniques, tools and tips of training management, with participants themselves designing, delivering and critiquing methods.

A suitable e-Learning portal will be identified during the project to deposit and make available all training materials produced; this will increase the ability to deliver 21st century learning and training opportunities.

Table 13: E-Learning and training.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist Groups	Development of Trainer of Trainers Programme and curriculum development	Number of Workshops Number of Trainees	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

A survey was conducted with all Directed partners including RWL hosts as part of Deliverable 6.3 Gaps and Opportunities assessment, knowledge transfer for training and education. The findings provided insights into partners' institutional knowledge, skills and attitudes around DRR/ CCA, existing and preferred training and educational activities, and collaboration opportunities with other projects, networks and platforms.

Based on findings, the initial knowledge transfer mechanisms selected include the development of learning materials/ resources (to embed in student and professional curriculum), in-person intensive learning activity (e.g. summer school), online learning programme (e.g. webinar or e-course), mentoring (e.g. students, interns) and cross-project collaboration (e.g. joint webinars). Such activities were identified to support capacity development activities in the RWLs (in line with the Capacity Development Strategy D1.2) and enhance training and education to wider target groups beyond the RWLs. Potential e-Learning platforms were identified, including the WeAdapt platform managed by partner SEI.

A co-design process for the development of learning resources will ensure that trainers and educators (within and beyond the project) are actively involved in the curriculum development and testing of learning resources/ activities for different target groups (Task 6.3) and selection of an e-Learning portal (D6.4) to collate the resources.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

Plan RWL knowledge exchange and learning webinar series including the identification of external speakers and cross-project collaboration opportunities.

- Conduct four Real World Lab knowledge exchange and learning webinar series.
- Test the use of the WeAdapt platform for hosting a webinar series and potential as suitable e-Learning platform.
- Planning the implementation of knowledge transfer activities and initial engagement of educators/trainers in co-design process of learning materials and curriculum development.

2.3.5 Published Papers

Academic journals – academic partners will target online high impact journals with academic research and new methodologies produced by the Project.

Table 14: Scientific publications.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Scientists & Researchers	Publication of at least 2 papers in high impact journals	Papers published Citations	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

No papers published at this point.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

A broad publication to be led by TUBS on the wider project to be developed in 2024.

2.3.6 Conference Attendance

Partners will attend and develop sessions for academic, public sector and business conferences to promote the new methodologies, data, tools/ tool-kits/ training packs and reports etc.

These conferences will include EGU, COP, ICLEI, Disaster Risk, ECCA, DRR and CCA conferences – to target specific audiences where relevant. Where possible stands will be located at larger conferences promoting the full outputs of the Project in the later part of the Project.

A short conference strategy will be designed to ensure that information is disseminated as widely as possible to target audiences.

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

Conference details and attendance by all partners can be found on pages 44 to 45 of this document.

Next Steps October 2023 -September 2024

Conference details and planned attendance by all partners can be found on pages 46 to 47 of this document.

2.3.6 Use of EU Communications & Dissemination Platforms

We will also seek support from EC communication hubs such as Climate Adapt, weADAPT and through other departments and platforms of the EC to disseminate our communications more broadly. We will receive guidance on this from ‘Next edition of the Secure Societies ‘Projects to Policy Seminar’ jointly organised by DG Home and REA in Brussels in June 2023

Table 15: EU communication and dissemination platforms.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
All	Publication of at least 4 articles or posts on EC platforms	Publications posted	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Update for October 2022 to September 2023

We attended the Secure Societies ‘Projects to Policy Seminar’ jointly organised by DG Home and REA in Brussels in June 2023 where we have received guidance on the various communications, dissemination and exploitations tools available to us, as well as met our sister projects under the call of this grant. We have since been involved with discussions with our sister projects, and continued cooperation have been agreed.

3.DIRECTED Story-board creation for partner communications and dissemination guidance

The DIRECTED Project has continued to plan strategic communications to work towards succeeding in the Projects objectives. The DIRECTED story board has been integrated into 2023/ 2024 communication and dissemination planning and will be updated and used beyond this period. The storyboard enables a focused approach to gaining influence to enable the Project and its partners to succeed in their goals, and increase communications, dissemination and broader innovation of the tools, governance recommendations and Data Fabric, rather than relying in broad brush communications

Figure 5: Story-board for content development.

Communications and dissemination actions required

- Clearly communicate and engage stakeholders in the main objectives of the DIRECTED Project
- Discuss the changes that need to occur for societal change in Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation
- Communicate & disseminate the activities required for change to happen
- Communicate & disseminate the potential impacts of change as well as the impacts of not changing/ adapting

Figure 6: Story-board for audience targeting.

Communications and dissemination actions required

- Focus communications on the stakeholder groups that can effect change
- Communicate and disseminate to upstream influencers of stakeholders that can effect change
- Ensure that communications and dissemination are conducted in styles that are familiar to the relevant stakeholders e.g. academic papers – for climate change scientists, informing MP’s, MEP’s through direct letters about the project, press releases for media bodies
- Don’t assume broad communications will reach them

Figure 7: Story-board for story development.

Communications and dissemination actions required

- Use the story structure in the DIRECTED Storyboard to create stories for your posts and communications
- Ensure that you involve the key characters in your stories, what did they experience, what did they say, use one or two quotes per communication
- Consider what evidence, results, reports and images you should use in DIRECTED posts – evidence-based posts are more powerful
- Including a sense of urgency in your communications, draws in readers, acts as a call to action

Figure 8: Story-board for story-telling development.

Communications and dissemination actions required

- Use relevant communications and dissemination tools to reach the right audiences.
- Record responses to communications and dissemination actions e.g. social media analytics, numbers and organisations at meetings, request for meetings, obtain analytics on publications where possible or readership numbers, post meeting questionnaires.
- Use your recording to understand how well we are doing with communications and dissemination and think about how it could be improved next time.
- Record any impacts of your communications and dissemination.

4. Year 1 – Dissemination & Communication Plan – Partner Reports

The following dissemination and communication plans are guided by the reporting structure of Horizon Europe.

“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”

“List the communication activities carried out in the context of the project. Use the same labels used in your DEC plan.”

The tables below directly correlate to the recording structure of Horizon Europe and are the planned work of the beneficiaries.

We will undergo further yearly communications and dissemination reviews to develop and improve the communications and dissemination we are undertaking. The review and planning phases are timetabled as follows;

- September 2023
- September 2024
- September 2025
- September 2026

4.1 Year 1 – Dissemination Plan Delivery Report

Table 16: Dissemination report year 1.

Name of Oasis Hub	Dissemination Activity Name	Type of Activity	Target Audience	Description of the objective(s) with Dissemination of DIRECTED Project	Status of Activity	Evidence of delivery - e.g. links, Presentation available	Date of delivery of dissemination	Audiences
TUBS	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submitted and accepted at EGU 2023	Delivered	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-13541	14-15 June 2023	Research communities EU Institutions
GIZ	Next edition of the Secure Societies 'Projects' Collaboration with EU	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submitted and accepted at TDH 2023	Delivered	https://directedproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/DIRECTED_Presentation_available	14-15 June 2023	Research communities EU Institutions
PIK	N/A staff not yet recruited for Project - activity will be submitted in the next report							
DTU	As the first year will be needed to get the Danube model into presentable shape, no dissemination activities are planned at this early stage of the project.							
DTU	Presentation of DIRECTED to the Danish Met	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) is presenting DIRECTED to the broader research community	Delivered	Poster available	16-11-2023	National authorities Research communities
DTU	Presented of DIRECTED at conference (lead)	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submitted and accepted at EGU	Delivered	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-13541		Research communities
DTU	Kick-off meeting(s) for Real World Lab (with C)	Education & training	Regional authorities	1st workshop planned (municipalities, industry)	Delivered	Meeting summaries prepared by RE3	March 2023, 2 May 2023	end user Industry
DTU	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Industry	Poster and Panel Participation at the Society	Delivered	https://sraeurope.eu/lund-sweden-2023-20	20 June 2023	Industry
DTU	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Regional authorities	REMTECH - https://www.remtechexpo.com/	Planned		Sep-23	Innovators
DTU	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Local authorities	Presentation at ECOMONDO Saferplaces/DII	Delivered	https://www.ecomondo.com/event/e		Nov-23 Civil society
RIFS	Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty Mid-Term	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submission to next the Midterm	Delivered	https://event.sdu.dk/coru2023/conference		Oct-23 Research communities
RIFS	Society for Risk Analysis annual meeting 2023	Conferences	Research communities	Research community abstract submission to next the Society for	Delivered	https://www.sra.org/events-webinars/ai		Dec-23 Research communities
SEI	ToT on Tandem knowledge co-production from Education & training	Education & training	Local authorities	A co-designed and co-developed "Training A diversity of audiences in the RWL as well as researchers to be hosted on an e-	Planned	Currently in review for publishing		Research communities
SEI	ToT modules	Other	Local authorities		Planned			
UCC	EGU 2023 conference presentation	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submission on "Implications of Outreach with local schools"	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity-7064541862279139329-ZjUf?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member		
UCC	UNIC PROCOMMS workshop in Cork, Ireland	Collaboration with EU	Local authorities	Running a 'Climate in a Box' activity in local	Delivered			
UCC	Action Research Summer Camp (attendee)	Education & training	Other	This summer camp in Innsbruck, Austria	Delivered			
UCC	6th European Climate Change Adaptation	Conferences	Research communities	Directed poster will be submitted.	Delivered	https://directedproject.eu/#news		
UCC	19th Annual Law and the Environment	Conferences	Research communities	Session accepted including a presentation	Delivered	https://x.com/LydiaCumiskey/status/1649022033156530176?s=20		
UCC	BlueConnections Conference	Conferences	Research communities	Session	Delivered	https://x.com/LydiaCumiskey/status/17		
ETH REGIONH	N/A staff not yet recruited for Project - activity will be submitted in the next report							
ETH REGIONH	Kick-off meeting for Real World Lab, Capital R	Education & training	end user	Mapping of barriers and challenges in DRR/C	Delivered			end user
ETH REGIONH	Establish a communication forum between the	Meetings	Industry	Secure smooth contact between the project's	Ongoing	No separate communication forum is	Ongoing throughout the year.	Industry
ETH REGIONH	Yearly updates on DIRECTED's results for poli	Meetings	Regional authorities	Secure political support, maximise result's im	Planned (8th of Febru	https://www.regionh.dk/politik/nye-m	8th of February 2023	Regional authorities
ETH REGIONH	One article in a professional journal/magazine	Other scientific collaboration	Industry	Maximise result's impact	Planned	Not delivered yet. Planned for next phase.		Industry
ETH REGIONH	Awareness-building with stakeholders	Meetings	end user	Stakeholder engagement	Ongoing	Several online meetings and two ph	Ongoing throughout the year.	end user
ARSTPC-ER	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	REMTECH - https://www.remtechexpo.com/	Delivered			
ARSTPC-ER	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	ECOMONDO https://www.ecomondo.com/	Delivered			
ARSTPC-ER	Webinar	Education & training	end user	Webinar or Real Game/Exercise with other	Delivered			
ARSTPC-ER	First RWL2 Meeting	Meetings	end user	DIRECTED project presentation to the	Delivered			
ARSTPC-ER	Second RWL2 Meeting	Meetings	end user	Sharing of operational steps with	Delivered			
ARSTPC-ER	Collaboration with other EU funded project	Collaboration with EU	Research communities	STREAM PROJECT - Comacchio Test Site	Ongoing			
G&C	Awareness-building with stakeholders, potentia	Meetings	Industry	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder	Ongoing	e.g. in person Meetings with represe	of Generali (29.11.23) and Uniq (27.11.23)	
G&C	RWL Stakeholder input gathering workshop	Education & training	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder	Planned			
G&C	Information events in RWL (e.g. invite local au	Meetings	Local authorities		Ongoing	e.g. in person Meetings with represe	29/11/23	
G&C	Tool demonstration (Future Danube Model)	Meetings	Industry		Ongoing			
G&C	Contribution to related events and seminars (e	Conferences	Industry		Ongoing	DAFF – Budapest	11/10/23	
IASA	Presentation during Youngs Summer Scientist	Meetings	Research communities		Delivered			
IASA	international PhD students.	Other scientific collaboration			Delivered			
EV	Awareness-building with stakeholders	Meetings	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder	Ongoing	meeting minutes available	19.04.2023, 29.06.2023	
EV	RWL Stakeholder input gathering workshop	Education & training	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder	Ongoing	meeting minutes available	19.04.2023, 29.06.2023	
EV	Information events in RWL	Meetings	Local authorities		Ongoing	meeting minutes available	19.04.2023, 29.06.2023	
EV	DIRECTED meeting Cologne	Meetings	Other		Delivered	agenda of the meeting available	18. - 22.09.2023	
52*North	OGC Innovation Days, Disaster Resilience	Conferences	Research communities	New tools and technologies for wildfire and	Delivered	https://52north.org/events/ogc-innov	December 7, 2022	Research communities
52*North	EGU 2023 conference joint presentation (co-a	Conferences	Research communities	Innovations for multi-sectoral impact	Delivered	https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.	23-28 April 2023	Research communities
52*North	Geospatial World Forum	Conferences	Other	Connecting Data and Models across stakeho	Delivered	https://52north.org/events/geospatia	Friday, May 5, 2023	Other
52*North	Data Week Leipzig 2023	Conferences	Industry	Climate Services using Open Data & Open AI	Delivered	https://2023.dataweek.de/en/2023-0	June 27, 2023	Industry
52*North	IFI Forum	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Overview of Project goals and 52*North's arc	Planned			
52*North	IZG-Sommerprogramm 2023	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Overview of Project goals and 52*North's arc	Delivered	http://www.izg.rub.de/veranstaltungen	June 16, 2023	Research communities
52*North	DIRECTED meeting Cologne	Meetings	other		Planned	18. - 22.09.2023		Research communities
52*North	Scientific and Technical Advisory Board	Meetings	Research communities	Overview of Project goals and 52*North's arc	Delivered	https://52north.org/events/52north-s	December 13, 2022	Research communities
52*North	Shareholders Assembly	Meetings	other	Overview of Project goals and 52*North's arc	Delivered	https://52north.org/events/52north-s	March 13, 2023	Research communities
ZSRT	Contacting stakeholders.	Meetings	business partners	Contacting stakeholders, identifying the key	Delivered	meeting minutes available	05/05/2023	Research communities
ZSRT	Awareness raising at regional level.	Education & training	National authorities	First intro of DIRECTED at national level.	Delivered	meeting minutes and photos availab	20/04/2023	National authorities
ZSRT	Awareness raising at regional level.	Education & training	Regional authorities	First intro of DIRECTED at regional level.	Delivered	meeting minutes and photos availab	19/04/2023	Regional authorities
ARPAE	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	REMTECH - https://www.remtechexpo.com/	Planned	TBC		
ARPAE	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	ECOMONDO https://www.ecomondo.com/	Planned			
ARPAE	Meeting	Meetings	end user	2/3 meetings with RWL2 Stakeholders on	Planned			
ARPAE	Collaboration with other EU funded project	Collaboration with EU	Research communities	STREAM PROJECT - Comacchio Test Site	Ongoing			

4.3 Year 2 – Dissemination Plan

Table 18: Dissemination plan year 2.

Name of Oasis Hub	Dissemination Activity Name	Type of Dissemination	Target Audience Reached	Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of Activity
Oasis Hub	Case Study Creation and Dissemination	Education & training	Other	Case study reporting events in Rhine Erft & Emilia Romagna floods	Ongoing
	Publication of deliverable reports on website	Education & training	Research communities	Publication of open and informative deliverable reports from all partners on website	Planned
TUBS	Development of a series of at least 4 podcasts/webinars for cross real world lab dissemination, know	Short video/webinar/podcast	Civil Society	Short video/webinar/podcast	Planned
	Cross-project Workshops jointly organized with EU Partner Projects	Workshop	Research communities	Cross-project knowledge exchange and collaboration	planned
	Journal article, systematic literature review	Other	Research communities	Review on co-production in DRM/CCA research and practice	ongoing
GIZ	Presentation at Tag der Hydrologie 24	Conferences	Research communities	Talk and/or Poster presentation at EGU24 in Vienna	planned
	Presentation at 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World	Conferences	Research communities	Talk and/or Poster presentation at TDH24 in Berlin	planned
	Attendance at CERIS DRS events	Clustering Activities	Policy makers and research communities	Talk and/or Poster presentation in Amsterdam	planned
PIK	Presentations at relevant conferences (EGU24 and Tag der Hydrologie 24)	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation and Panel discussion in Brussels	Planned
	Publishing the work done in the RWLs and WPs as presentations/posters in national and international conferences suitable for presenting our models.	Conferences	Research communities	Posters	Planned
DTU	Dissemination through regular workshop series at Danish Meteorological Institute	Other scientific collaboration	National authorities	Scientific collaboration with a focus on RWL1, WP2	Ongoing
	Present DIRECTED project at scientific conferences and exhibition	Conferences	Local authorities	Presentation at ECOMONDO Saferplaces/DIRECTED https://www.ecomondo.com	Delivered
RIFS	Dissemination participating at Scientific Conferences and Innovation Ecosystems	Conferences	Innovators	presentation of Systemic Risk Governance Framework, focus on WP3	Planned
	PIK Conference "Cross-border climate change impacts and systemic risks in Europe"	Conferences	Research communities	Framework, focus on WP3	planned
SEI	Workshop on Systemic Risks at the RIFS	Conferences	Research communities	Framework, focus on WP3	planned
	SRA Conference in Washington DC	Conferences	Research communities	shared implementation and adaptation of IAD framework	planned
	Workshop to integrate IAD framework into RWL stakeholder engagement strategy	Education & training	end user	Literature Review	Ongoing
UCC	Journal article, systematic literature review	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Framework Development	ongoing
	Journal article, systemic risks and societal tipping points	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Co-Production and Sit	planned
	Proposed collaboration with RWL Capital Region of Copenhagen - implement	Co-Production and Sit	Regional authorities	Event (conference/meeting/workshop/ internet debate/ round table/ group discussion)	planned
ETH	Society for Risk Analysis annual meeting 2024, December 9-11, 2024, Austin, USA: The DIRECTED	Research communities	Research communities	Event (conference/meeting/workshop/ internet debate/ round table/ group discussion)	planned
	Society for Risk Analysis Europe annual meeting 2024, June 3-5, 2024, Athens: presentation of Risk	Research communities	Research communities	Session planned on an Adaptation Action Academy. Capacity development	Planned
REGIONH	SEI Science Forum	Conferences	Research communities	A co-designed and co-developed "Training of Trainers" programme is being implemented	Ongoing
	ToT modules on Risk-Tandem framework	Education & training	Local authorities	Journal article on co-production and practical challenges/Risk-Tandem	Planned
	Journal article, systematic literature review	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities		Delivered
ARSTPC-ER	UNIC PROCOMMS workshop in Cork, Ireland (26th Oct 2023)	Collaboration with EU	Local authorities		Planned
	UNIC PROCOMMS workshop in Malmö Sweden (31st Jan 2024)	Collaboration with EU	Local authorities		Planned
	Irish National Hydrology Conference (Nov 2023)	Conferences	National authorities	Directed poster presented – see here	Delivered
G&C	EGU 2024 (14-19 April)	Conferences	Research communities	Convening session Operational forecasting and warning systems for	planned
	3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World	Conferences	Research communities	Convening session Science for policy and practice: Synergising DRR and CCA	Planned
IASA	Development of a webinar series for cross real world lab dissemination, know	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Event (conference/meeting/workshop/ internet debate/ round table/ group discussion)	200 viewers
	Journal article, systematic literature review	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities		
52°North	Abstract submission	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submission	Planned
	CLIMADA days 2024	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Present the first version of the Multi-Criteria tool	Planned
	2nd workshop for all stakeholders in RWL1	Meetings	end user	A step closer to the stakeholders needs in order to develop Directed's solutions	Planned
ARPAE	Yearly updates on DIRECTED's results for policy makers in REGIONH	Meetings	Regional authorities	Secure political support, maximise result's impact (especially related to governance)	Planned
	One article in a professional journal/magazine/website (e.g. watertech).	Other scientific collaboration	Industry	Maximise results' impact	Planned
	Webinar about DIRECTED's results through the national network of climate adaptation	Education & training	end user	Maximise results' impact	Planned
ZSRT	Presentations at relevant conferences	Education & training	end user	Maximise results' impact	Ongoing
	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	ECOMONDO https://www.ecomondo.com	Planned
G&C	Meeting	Meetings	National authorities	workshop in Rimini - June 2024	Ongoing
	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	REMTTECH - https://www.remttechexpo.com	Planned
	Collaboration with other EU funded project	Collaboration with EU	Research communities	STREAM PROJECT - Comacchio Test Site	Planned
IASA	Collaboration with National Civil Protection Department	Education & training	end user	joint exercise	Ongoing
	Awareness-building with stakeholders, potential clients & partners	Meetings	Industry	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	Planned
EV	RWL Stakeholder input gathering workshop	Education & training	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	Planned
	Information events in RWL (e.g. invite local authorities etc.)	Meetings	Local authorities		Planned
52°North	Tool demonstration (Future Danube Model)	Meetings	Industry		Planned
	Contribution to related events and seminars (e.g. DRMKC, ICPDR events)	Conferences	Industry		Planned
ARPAE	Journal article, systematic literature review	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities		
	Stakeholder meetings	Meetings	end user	WP1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	Ongoing
ZSRT	Workshop with decision makers from federal districts	Education & training	local authorities	workshop on situation assessment for potentially hazardous weather	Planned
	Poster - Tag der Hydrologie	Conferences	Research communities	Poster at conference	Planned
ARPAE	Scientific and Technical Advisory Board	Meetings	research communities	update Project work	Planned
	Shareholders Assembly	Meetings	industry	update Project work	Planned
	geoENV2024	conferences	research communities	Climate Services	Planned
	EGU 2024	conferences	research communities	Climate Services	Planned
	AGILE 2024	conferences	research communities	Climate Services	Planned
	GEOSTAT32024	conferences	research communities	forecasting	Planned
	FOSSGIS 2024	conferences	research communities	Climate Services	Planned
	OASIS Insight Loss modeling framework	conferences	research communities	forecasting	Planned
	Aon Benfield miniconference series	conferences	research communities	forecasting	Planned
	Staff Meetings	meetings	other	status of work	Planned
ARPAE	IIGI Forum	meetings	other	Project Overview with focus on 52°North activities	Planned
	TBC				
ZSRT	Project page on DIRECTED	Other	Civil society	We plan to create an expanded informative content and sub-page on the As	Planned
	Collaboration with National Civil Protection Department	Education & training	National authorities	We would like to develop closer cooperation with disaster management experts	Planned
ZSRT	Awareness-building with stakeholders, potential clients & partners	Education & training	Local authorities	What we have found in the first year is that messages and engagement efforts	Planned
	Stakeholder meetings	Meetings	Regional authorities	We will join the professional events at which the relevant local authorities are	Planned

4.3 Year 2 – Communication Plan

Table 19: Communication plan year 2.

Name of Beneficiary	Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Audience	Communication Channel	Outcome	Status
Oasis Hub	Directed storyboard creation	Storyboard for messaging for the project	Specific user communities			Ongoing
	Four blogs from Oct 2023 to Sept 2024	Blogs - on various aspects of the project	Civil Society	Media Article	500 readers	Planned
	Bi weekly social media posts across social media channels	Reporting on progress of DIRECTED Project	Civil Society	Social Media	25 posts/ @ @2500 impressions	Ongoing
	Four short videos or podcasts aimed at social media	Podcasts to include Real World Lab Report	Civil Society	Social Media	400 views	Planned
	Completion of 4th Real World Lab brochures & translations	Printed downloadable information	Civil Society	Print materials	400 downloads	Ongoing
	Improvement to website	Improvement to website to include Product	Citizens	Social Media	4000 views per annum	Planned
	Four news pieces – focused on RWL meetings	News on RWL meetings	Citizens	Social Media	400 views	Planned
	Social media content/ storyline plan	Plan for social media coverage in 2023/2024	Citizens	Social Media	Plan	Ongoing
	Engagement of social media influencers	Engagement of social media influencers in	Specific user communities	Social Media	Reposts by influencers of social media c	Planned
	Short 3 min – intro video for DIRECTED	Short intro video	Citizens	Social Media	200 views	Planned
	Translation of all RWL leaflets into local languages	Translation of RWL leaflets	Citizens	Print materials	400 users	Planned
	Completion of Danish Leaflet in English.	Leaflet	Citizens	Print materials	100 users	Planned
	Press release for at least 2-3 RWL Meetings	Press release	Citizens	Media Article	2-4 media articles	Planned
	Completion of Yr 2 Communications and Dissemination Report	Report	EU Institutions	Print materials	Report posted by EU	Planned
	TUBS	General promotion of DIRECTED via project website		Research communities, Civil Society	Social Media	
Involvement in 2 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars		Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	100 viewers	Planned
GFZ	Promotion of the project via the project and GFZ websites by contributing/uploading material		Research communities	Website		Planned
	Publishing articles in national/international scientific journals		Research communities	Publications		Planned
PIK	Contributing material for the projects social media activities		stakeholders and public	Website		Planned
	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short podcast/ webinar	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
DTU	Contribute material for the project website	Visualizations from Danube Model outputs	Research communities	Website		Planned
	Publishing at least one article on insights from the Danube RWL in international scientific journals	International scientific journals	Research communities	Print materials		Planned
GECO	The Danube model should be presented at relevant meetings, especially	Presentation with slides	Specific user communities	Event (conference/n	~25 attendees at DAFF, Budapest	Ongoing
	Involvement in 1 short video/ podcast/ webinar	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
DTU	One article in a broad media outlet		Civil Society	Media Article	Awareness of DIRECTED in Denmark	Planned
	Press release (with Region H) - postponed from last phase	Launch a Press Release with a Danish focus	Industry/business partners	Press Release		Planned
GECO	Presentation of modelling tools at RWL1 workshop (May 2024, planned)	Presentation with slides, potentially demo	Specific user communities	Event (conference/n	Approx. 25 attendees in RWL1	Planned
	Preparation and submission of at least 2 papers in international scientific journals	2-3 papers in preparation with relation to DIR	Research communities	Print materials		Planned
GECO	Presentations at international scientific conferences and national events	Presentation with slides	Specific user communities	Event (conference/n	NA	Planned
	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
GECO	Communication DIRECTED outcomes and activities via Web Site, Press Release and Social Media		Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
	Communication during RWL meeting about Saferplaces functionalities		Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
RIFS	Saferplaces and DIRECTED press release	News Saferplaces web site	Civil Society	Press Release		Delivered
	Shared post on LinkedIn	LinkedIn Post on Saferplaces role in DIRECTED	Civil Society	Social Media		Delivered
SEI	Planned engagement with DIRECTED Podcast	Podcast/ webinar	Civil Society	Social Media		Planned
	Share news/posts from DIRECTED social media	Updates from the project	Research communities	Social Media		Planned
UCC	Institutional project page on DIRECTED	Updating page with relevant project outputs	Research communities	Social Media	Awareness raising and opportunities for	Ongoing
	Share news/posts from DIRECTED social media	Updates from the project	Research communities	Social Media	Awareness raising and opportunities for	Ongoing
UCC	Share news/posts from DIRECTED weADAPT	Updates from the project and especially from International organisational	Research communities	Social Media	Awareness raising and opportunities for	Ongoing
	Presenting Risk Tandem updates and delivering capacity development modules	Updated risk tandem and learning modules	Specific user communities	Event (conference/n	Sharing information	Ongoing
ETH REGIONH	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
	Project page on DIRECTED	Updating page with relevant project outputs	Research communities	Social Media		Ongoing
ETH REGIONH	Share news/posts from DIRECTED social media	Updates from the project	Research communities	Social Media		Ongoing
	At least one blog post on DIRECTED activities	Knowledge co-production / Risk-Tandem in	Research communities	Social Media		Planned
ETH REGIONH	One paper on Risk-Tandem / knowledge co-production approach	Collaboration with WP3 and 4 colleagues	Research communities	Social Media		Planned
	Awareness-building with RWL stakeholders, potential clients & partners	Demo risk maps and multi-criteria adaption local authorities			Awareness raising and opportunities for	Ongoing
ARSTPC-ER	One article in a broad media outlet		Civil Society	Media Article	Awareness of DIRECTED in Denmark	Planned
	SoMe in relation to significant milestones. For instans the stakeholder workshop on data and organisational challenges		Industry/business partners	Social Media	Awareness building for stakeholders	Ongoing
ARSTPC-ER	Re-posting of Directed social media communications	Short intro video/ podcasts	Industry/business partners	Social Media	Awareness building for stakeholders	Ongoing
	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars		Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
G&C	Article on Directed website of Emilia-Romagna Region		Civil Society	Media Article	Awareness of DIRECTED in Italy	Ongoing
	Posting on Instagram, Youtube		Civil Society	Social Media	Awareness of DIRECTED in Italy	Ongoing
G&C	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
	Quarterly blog on website	Status RWL Danube	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Planned
IIASA	Information stand during GISAR Symposium 2024 and in G&Co office	Description of the project goals and RWL	Industry/business partners	Print materials		Planned
	Awareness building of DRM capabilities	Description of the project goals and RWL	Industry/business partners	Print materials		Planned
EV	Re-posting of Directed social media communications	The overall project communications	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Planned
	Stakeholder interviews	Collecting first hand information	Industry/business partners	Interview		Planned
52°North	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
	TBC					
ARPAAE	Newsletter for stakeholders	Newsletter with updates on DIRECTED	local authorities	newsletter	sharing information	planned
	Newsletter „Infofluss“ EV members	Newsletter with updates on DIRECTED	Industry/business partners	newsletter	sharing information	planned
52°North	Post on EV website	Inform and give updates on DIRECTED	Civil Society	press release	sharing information	planned
	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
ZSRT	Re-posting of Directed social media communications	The overall project communications	Industry/business partners	Social Media	sharing information	ongoing
	1 pager about DIRECTED as project reference on website	Description of project goals including focus	Industry/business partners	Print materials	sharing information	planned
ZSRT	Involvement in 1 short videos/ podcasts/ webinars	Short intro video/ podcasts	Civil Society	Social Media	50 viewers	Planned
	TBC					
ZSRT	Re-posting of Directed social media communications	The overall project communications	Industry/business partners	Social Media	increase the number of supporters (regl	Planned
	Contribute material for the project website	Using our professional network, we plan to	Research communities	Print materials	increase the number of readers, increas	Planned
ZSRT	Project Press Release	Other	Civil society	What we have found	Planned	

Partners

